

ENVIRONMENTAL TREATIES AND LEGISLATION

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Abstract

To address environmental issues that India and other countries face, it is essential and very important to commence action at all levels like global, regional, national, local, and community. It is not adequate to have international agreements, treaties and instruments on environmental issues and various problems but completion, implementation and enforcement of these policies and agreements to a large extent determine their impact and effectiveness. In the last few decades, there has been an increasing concern and consciousness about the need to protect the environment, nationally and internationally. Under the structure of the Indian Constitution, a number of Articles are enumerated in which environmental duties to preserve the natural resources of the country have been stated like Articles 48-A and 51-A[g]. Additionally, the Constitution also provides procedures in Articles 252 and 253 for adopting national legislations in regard to the needs of the States. The constitutional mandates and other environmental laws or regulations in India effective, successful and urgent need to streamline enforcement. The creative and innovative role of Indian Judiciary and National Green Tribunal [NGT] has been significant and laudable in this era. In this research paper, an effort has been made to momentarily outline the various Indian legislations and international treaties relating to the environment, which are mainly and more relevant to protect and improve the environment in India. The enforcement, scope and limit of these legislations has also been critically examined and evaluated in systematically manner. Protection of the environment and keeping ecological balance in Indian scenario unaffected is a task which not only the Government but also every individual, association, society, industry and corporation must undertake. It is a social compulsion and fundamental duty enshrined in Article 51-A[g] of the Indian Constitution.

Key word: Environmental Protection, International Treaties, Conventions, Environmental Laws.

Introduction

What is the object or purpose of International Environmental Law, is it an ethical statement, deterrence or a socializing instrument? If it is an ethical statement, which many of the framework or agenda conventions seem to be, is it merely inspirational? If it is anticipated as deterrence, why are there not more international forums for dispute resolution, empowered to enforce agreements? If it is intended as a socialization method, is it working? To address environmental issues that India and other countries face, it is essential and very important to commence action at all levels like global, regional, national, local, and community. It is not adequate to have international agreements and instruments on environmental issues and various

problems but completion, implementation and enforcement of these policies and agreements to a large extent determine their impact and effectiveness.

In the last few decades, there has been an increasing concern and consciousness about the need to protect the environment, nationally and internationally. Under the structure of the Constitution of India, a number of Articles are enumerated in which environmental duties to preserve the natural resources of the country have been stated like **Articles 48–A** and **51–A[g]**. Additionally, the Constitution also provides procedures³ in Articles 252 and 253 for adopting national legislations in regard to the needs of the State. The Union or Central Government of India, in pursuance of the Stockholm Declaration of 1972 and acting under **Article 253**, adopted the **Water [Prevention and Control of Pollution] Act, 1974** and the **Water [Prevention and Control of Pollution] Cess Act, 1977**.

In this present paper, an effort has been made to momentarily outline the various Indian legislations and international treaties relating to the environment, which are mainly and more relevant to protect and improve the environment in India. The enforcement, scope and limit of these legislations has also been critically examined and evaluated in systematically manner.

Environmental Treaties

An international environmental convention is a **legally binding agreement** negotiated among governments to take action together to combat or mitigate a global environmental threat. Reaching an agreement to take such action among sovereign nations with diverse interests is no small feat. However, in recent decades, such agreements have proliferated to address international environmental concerns at the global and regional levels. Some famous environmental treaties are listed below:-

- 1. Ramsar Convention (1971): The Ramsar Convention on Wetlands of International Importance Especially as Waterfowl Habitat** is an international treaty for the conservation and sustainable use of Ramsar sites (wetlands). It is also known as the **Convention on Wetlands**. It is named after the city of Ramsar in Iran, where the convention was signed in 1971. Every three years, representatives of the contracting parties meet as the Conference of Contracting Parties (COP), the policy-making organ of the convention which adopts decisions (site designations, resolutions and recommendations) to administer the work of the convention and improve the way in which the parties are able to implement its objectives. In 2022, COP14 was co-held in Wuhan, China, and Geneva, Switzerland.
- 2. Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) (1973):** It is an **international agreement** to which States and regional economic integration organizations adhere voluntarily. CITES was drafted as a result of a resolution adopted in 1963 at a meeting of members of the **International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)**. CITES entered into force in **July 1975**. Currently there are 184 Parties including countries or regional economic integration organizations. The objective of this convention is to ensure that **international trade** in specimens of wild animals and plants

does not threaten their survival.

- 3. Vienna Convention (1985): The Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer** is a multilateral environmental agreement signed in 1985 that provided frameworks for international reductions in the production of chlorofluorocarbons due to their contribution to the destruction of the ozone layer, resulting in an increased threat of skin cancer.
- 4. Basel Convention (1989): The Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal**, usually known as the **Basel Convention**, is an international treaty that was designed to reduce the movements of hazardous waste between nations, and specifically to prevent transfer of hazardous waste from developed to less developed countries. It does not, however, address the movement of radioactive waste. The convention is also intended to minimize the rate and toxicity of wastes generated, to ensure their environmentally sound management as closely as possible to the source of generation, and to assist developing countries in environmentally sound management of the hazardous and other wastes they generate.
- 5. Rio Earth Summit (1992): The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED)**, also known as the Rio Conference or the Earth Summit, was a major United Nations Conference held in Rio De Jenerio from 3 to 14 June 1992. Earth Summit was created as a response for member states to cooperate together internationally on development issues after the Cold War. Due to issues relating to sustainability being too big for individual member states to handle, Earth Summit was held as a platform for other member states to collaborate.
- 6. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (1992):** It is an international treaty among countries to combat "dangerous human interference with the climate system", in part by stabilizing greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere. It was signed in 1992 by 154 states at the **United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED)**, informally known as the Earth Summit, held in Rio de Janeiro. Its secretariat was in Geneva at first but relocated to Bonn in 1996. The treaty entered into force on 21 March 1994. "UNFCCC" is also the name of the Secretariat charged with supporting the operation of the convention, with offices on the UN Campus in Bonn, Germany.
- 7. Kyoto Protocol (1997): The Kyoto Protocol** was an international treaty which extended the 1992 United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) that commits state parties to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, based on the scientific consensus that global warming is occurring and that human-made CO₂ emissions are driving it. The Kyoto Protocol was adopted in Kyoto, Japan, on 11 December 1997 and entered into force on 16 February 2005. There were 192 parties to the Protocol in 2020. The Kyoto Protocol implemented the objective of the UNFCCC to reduce the onset of global warming by reducing greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere to "a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system"

- 8. Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety (2000): The Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety to the Convention on Biological Diversity** is an international agreement on biosafety as a supplement to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) effective since 2003. The Biosafety Protocol seeks to protect biological diversity from the potential risks posed by genetically modified organisms resulting from modern biotechnology. The Biosafety Protocol makes clear that products from new technologies must be based on the precautionary principle and allow developing nations to balance public health against economic benefits. It will for example let countries ban imports of genetically modified organisms if they feel there is not enough scientific evidence that the product is safe and requires exporters to label shipments containing genetically altered commodities such as corn or cotton.
- 9. Stockholm Convention (2001): Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants** is an international environmental treaty, signed on 22 May 2001 in Stockholm and effective from 17 May 2004, that aims to eliminate or restrict the production and use of persistent organic pollutants (POPs). Key elements of the Convention include the requirement that developed countries provide new and additional financial resources and measures to eliminate production and use of intentionally produced POPs, eliminate unintentionally produced POPs where feasible, and manage and dispose of POPs wastes in an environmentally sound manner. Precaution is exercised throughout the Stockholm Convention, with specific references in the preamble, the objective, and the provision on identifying new POPs.
- 10. Nagoya Protocol (2010): The Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from their Utilization to the Convention on Biological Diversity, also known as the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS)** is a 2010 supplementary agreement to the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). Its aim is the implementation of one of the three objectives of the CBD: the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources, thereby contributing to the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity. It sets out obligations for its contracting parties to take measures in relation to access to genetic resources, benefit-sharing and compliance. The protocol was adopted on 29 October 2010 in Nagoya, Japan, and entered into force on 12 October 2014. As of April 2022 it has been ratified by 137 parties, which includes 136 UN member states and the European Union.
- 11. United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP 21) (2015): The 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference, COP 21 or CMP 11** was held in Paris, France, from 30 November to 12 December 2015. It was the 21st yearly session of the Conference of the Parties (COP) to the 1992 United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the 11th session of the Meeting of the Parties (CMP) to the 1997 Kyoto Protocol. The conference negotiated the Paris Agreement, a global agreement on the reduction of climate change, the text of which represented a consensus of the

representatives of the 196 attending parties. The agreement was due to enter into force when joined by at least 55 countries which together represented at least 55 percent of global greenhouse gas emissions. A target reached on 4 November 2016. On 22 April 2016 (Earth Day), 174 countries signed the agreement in New York, and began adopting it within their own legal systems.

12. United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP 24) (2018): The 2018 United Nations Climate Change Conference, more commonly referred to as the Katowice Climate Change Conference or COP24, was the 24th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. It was held between 2 and 15 December 2018 in Katowice, Poland. The conference was held in the International Congress Centre. The president of COP24 was Michal Kurtyka. The conference also incorporated the fourteenth meeting of the parties for the Kyoto Protocol (CMP14), and the third session of the first meeting of the parties for the Paris Agreement (CMA1-3 or CMA1.3) which agreed on rules to implement the Agreement. The conference's objective was to have a full implementation of the Paris agreement.

13. United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP 25) (2019): The 2019 United Nations Climate Change Conference, also known as COP25, was the 25th United Nations Climate Change conference. It was held in Madrid, Spain, from 2 to 13 December 2019 under the presidency of the Chilean government. The conference incorporated the 25th Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the 15th meeting of the parties to the Kyoto Protocol (CMP15), and the second meeting of the parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA2).

Needs of Environmental Treaties

The environmental treaties are very important for the world because of the following reasons:

- Ratification and implementation of the Convention and its protocols will, for many Parties, reduce health and environmental impacts more cost-effectively than unilateral action.
- It also creates economic benefits as harmonized legislation and standards across borders will introduce a level playing field for industry across countries and prevent Parties from competing with each other at the expense of the environment and health.
- Factors that harm human health, affect food security, hinder economic development, contribute to climate change and degrade the environment upon which our very livelihoods depend.
- The Convention provides a platform to discuss these interconnections and takes actions to prevent negative impacts.

Environmental Legislation

Environmental laws are laws that protect the environment. Environmental law is the collection of laws, regulations, agreements and common law that governs how humans interact with their environment. This includes environmental regulations; laws governing management of natural

resources, such as forests, minerals, or fisheries; and related topics such as environmental impact assessments. Environmental law is seen as the body of laws concerned with the protection of living things (human beings inclusive) from the harm that human activity may immediately or eventually cause to them or their species, either directly or to the media and the habits on which they depend.

Principles

Environmental law has developed in response to emerging awareness of and concern over issues impacting the entire world. While laws have developed piecemeal and for a variety of reasons, some effort has gone into identifying key concepts and guiding principles common as a whole. The principles discussed below are not an exhaustive list and are not universally recognized or accepted. Nonetheless, they represent important principles for the understanding of environmental law around the world.

- **Sustainable Development:** It is defined by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs," sustainable development may be considered together with the concepts of "integration" (development cannot be considered in isolation from sustainability) and "interdependence" (social and economic development, and environmental protection, are interdependent). Laws mandating environmental impact assessment and requiring or encouraging development to minimize environmental impacts may be assessed against this principle.

The modern concept of sustainable development was a topic of discussion at the **1972 United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (Stockholm Conference)**, and the driving force behind the **1983 World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, or Bruntland Commission)**. In 1992, the first UN Earth Summit resulted in the Rio Declaration, Principle 3 of which reads: "The right to development must be fulfilled so as to equitably meet developmental and environmental needs of present and future generations." Sustainable development has been a core concept of international environmental discussion ever since, including at the **World Summit on Sustainable Development (Earth Summit 2002)**, and the **United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development**.

- **Equity:** It is defined by UNEP to include intergenerational equity – "the right of future generations to enjoy a fair level of the common patrimony" – and intergenerational equity – "the right of all people within the current generation to fair access to the current generation's entitlement to the Earth's natural resources" – environmental equity considers the present generation under an obligation to account for long-term impacts of activities, and to act to sustain the global environment and resource base for future generations. Pollution control and resource management laws may be assessed against this principle.
- **Tran's boundary Responsibility:** It is defined in the international law context as an

obligation to protect one's own environment, and to prevent damage to neighboring environments, UNEP considers Trans boundary responsibility at the international level as a potential limitation on the rights of the sovereign state. Laws that act to limit externalities imposed upon human health and the environment may be assessed against this principle

- **Public Participation of Transparency:** Identified as essential conditions for "accountable governments,... industrial concerns," and organizations generally, public participation and transparency are presented by UNEP as requiring "effective protection of the human right to hold and express opinions and to seek, receive and impart ideas,... a right of access to appropriate, comprehensible and timely information held by governments and industrial concerns on economic and social policies regarding the sustainable use of natural resources and the protection of the environment, without imposing undue financial burdens upon the applicants and with adequate protection of privacy and business confidentiality," and "effective judicial and administrative proceedings." These principles are present in environmental impact assessment, laws requiring publication and access to relevant environmental data, and administrative procedure.

Environmental Legislation around the World

- **Africa:** According to the **International Network for Environmental Compliance and Enforcement (INECE)**, the major environmental issues in Africa are "drought and flooding, air pollution, deforestation, loss of biodiversity, freshwater availability, degradation of soil and vegetation, and widespread poverty. The **U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)** is focused on the "growing urban and industrial pollution, water quality, and electronic waste and indoor air from cookstoves. They hope to provide enough aid on concerns regarding pollution before their impacts contaminate the African environment as well as the global environment. By doing so they intend to "protect human health, particularly vulnerable populations such as children and the poor. In order to accomplish these goals in Africa, EPA programs are focused on strengthening the ability to enforce environmental laws as well as public compliance to them. Other programs work on developing stronger environmental laws, regulations, and standards.
- **Asia:** The **Asian Environmental Compliance and Enforcement Network (AECEN)** is an agreement between 16 Asian countries dedicated to improving cooperation with environmental laws in Asia. These countries include Cambodia, China, Indonesia, India, Maldives, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Nepal, Philippines, Pakistan, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Vietnam, and Lao PDR.
- **European Union:** The European Union issues secondary legislation on environmental issues that are valid throughout the EU (so called regulations) and many directives that must be implemented into national legislation from the 27 member states (national states). Examples are the **Regulation (EC) No. 338/97** on the implementation of CITES; or the

Natura 2000 network the centerpiece for nature & biodiversity policy, encompassing the bird Directive (79/409/EEC/ changed to 2009/147/EC) and the habitats directive (92/43/EEC). Which are made up of multiple SACs (Special Areas of Conservation, linked to the habitats directive) & SPAs (Special Protected Areas, linked to the bird directive), throughout Europe. EU legislation is ruled in Article 249 Treaty for the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). Topics for common EU legislation are:

- Climate Change
 - Air Pollution
 - Water Protection and management
 - Waste Management
 - Soil Protection
 - Protection of Nature, species and biodiversity
 - Noise Pollution
 - Cooperation for the environment with third countries (other than EU member states)
 - Civil Protection
- **Middle East:** Environmental law is rapidly growing in the Middle East. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency is working with countries in the Middle East to improve environmental governance, water pollution and water security, clean fuels and vehicles, public participation, and pollution prevention.
 - **Australia:** The **Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act 1999** is the centerpiece of environmental legislation in Australia. It sets up the "legal framework to protect and manage nationally and internationally important flora, fauna, ecological communities and heritage places" and focuses on protecting world heritage properties, national heritage properties, wetlands of international importance, nationally threatened species and ecological communities, migratory species, Commonwealth marine areas, Great Barrier Reef Marine Park, and the environment surrounding nuclear activities. However, it has been subject to numerous reviews examining its shortcomings, the latest taking place in mid-2020. The interim report of this review concluded that the laws created to protect unique species and habitats are ineffective.
 - **Oceania:** The main concerns about environmental issues in Oceania are "illegal releases of air and water pollutants, illegal logging timber trade, illegal shipment of hazardous wastes, including e-waste and ships slated for destruction, and insufficient institutional structure/lack of enforcement capacity". The **Secretariat of the Pacific Regional Environmental Programme (SPREP)** is an international organization between **Australia, the Cook Islands, FMS, Fiji, France, Kiribati, Marshall Islands, Nauru, New Zealand, Niue, Palau, PNG, Samoa, Solomon Island, Tonga, Tuvalu, US, and Vanuatu**. The SPREP was established in order to provide assistance in improving and protecting the environment as well as assure sustainable development for future

generations.

- **China:** According to the **U.S. Environmental Protection Agency**, "China has been working with great determination in recent years to develop, implement, and enforce a solid environmental law framework. Chinese officials face critical challenges in effectively implementing the laws, clarifying the roles of their national and provincial governments, and strengthening the operation of their legal system. Explosive economic and industrial growth in China has led to significant environmental degradation, and China is currently in the process of developing more stringent legal controls. The harmonization of Chinese society and the natural environment is billed as a rising policy priority. Environmental lawsuits have been available in China since the early 2000s. Public protest, however, plays a greater role in shaping China's Environmental Policy than litigation does.
- **Brazil:** The **Brazilian government created the Ministry of Environment in 1992** in order to develop better strategies for protecting the environment, using natural resources sustainably, and enforcing public environmental policies. The **Ministry of Environment** has authority over policies involving environment, water resources, preservation, and environmental programs involving the Amazon.
- **Canada:** The **Department of the Environment Act establishes the Department of the Environment in the Canadian government** as well as the position **Minister of the Environment**. Their duties include "the preservation and enhancement of the quality of the natural environment, including water, air and soil quality, renewable resources, including migratory birds and other non-domestic flora and fauna: water; meteorology;" The Environmental Protection Act is the main piece of Canadian environmental legislation that was put into place **March 31, 2000**. The Act focuses on "respecting pollution prevention and the protection of the environment and human health in order to contribute to sustainable development." Other principle federal statutes include the Canadian Environmental Assessment Act, and the Species at Risk Act. When provincial and federal legislation are in conflict federal legislation takes precedence, that being said individual provinces can have their own legislation such as **Ontario's Environmental Bill of Rights, and Clean Water Act**.

Environmental Legislation in India

In India, Environmental law is governed by the Environment Protection Act, 1986. This act is enforced by the Central Pollution Control Board and the numerous State Pollution Control Boards. Apart from this, there are also individual legislation specifically enacted for the protection of Water, Air, Wildlife, etc. Such legislations include:

- The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974
- The Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Act, 1977
- The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980
- The Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981
- Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) (Union Territories) Rules, 1983

- The Biological Diversity Act, 2002 and the Wild Life Protection Act, 1972
- Batteries (Management and Handling) Rules, 2001
- Recycled Plastics, Plastics Manufacture and Usage Rules, 1999
- The National Green Tribunal established under the National Green Tribunal Act of 2010 has jurisdiction over all environmental cases dealing with a substantial environmental question and acts covered under the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974.
- Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Cess Rules, 1978
- Ganga Action Plan, 1986
- The Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980
- Wildlife protection Act, 1972
- The Public Liability Insurance Act, 1991 and the Biological Diversity Act, 2002. The acts covered under Indian Wild Life Protection Act 1972 do not fall within the jurisdiction of the National Green Tribunal. Appeals can be filed in the Honorable Supreme Court of India.
- Basel Convention on Control of Transboundary Movements on Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal, 1989 and Its Protocols
- Hazardous Wastes (Management and Handling) Amendment Rules, 2003

Need of Environmental Legislation

The genesis of various national legislations lies in environmental issues. There should be effective legislation to protect the environment; otherwise, the growing population will create havoc and will destroy the environment. Another important aspect is the enforcement of these laws. We must vigorously and effectively enforce the law to protect our environment from further degradation and pollution. Pollution is an important factor, ignoring political territory and legislative jurisdiction. Therefore, environmental problems are global in nature. To prevent such problems, it is not only necessary to enact environmental laws at the national level but also the international level.

While modern society is increasingly concerned about global environmental issues, developing countries also have their complex, severe, and rapidly growing pollution problems. The potent combination of industrialization development and mass consumption trends is exacerbated by foreign companies operating with little regard for the impact on the local environment. Pollution is not just a health issue; it is a broader social issue, as pollution has the potential to destroy families and communities. Pollution issues are also closely related to the mode of development in developing countries. Nonetheless, many developing countries either do not have pollution control policies or do not have sufficient enforcement structures to ensure that policies are effective.

The combination of rapid industrial development (especially petrochemical and heavy industry), strong economic growth, and unprecedented urban expansion have substantially increased pollutant emissions.

Purpose of Environmental Legislation

The importance of environmental legislation is that environmental protection cannot be achieved without appropriate regulations and laws. Raising environmental awareness and promoting environmental education are the means by which people do not destroy the environment but protect it for the future. However, it is the legislation that ensures that environmental protection is actually implemented in everyday life. Legislation requires businesses, companies, the public, industries, etc., to protect the environment and prevent environmental degradation. It provides severe penalties for those who do not abide by the laws and rules. Ultimately, this type of enforcement ensures that ideas and plans are turned into practical efforts to protect the environment. At the international level, several environmental treaties and conventions attempt to address environmental issues. With the **Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment (1972)**, the United Nations began to emphasize environmental aspects. Since then, several nations have adopted seventy international treaties, declarations, charters, agreements, and so on. These efforts were made to safeguard the environment and balance human development with environmental conservation.

Conclusion

International efforts in coming up with common strategies in addressing various environmental issues are confronted by not just economic and ecological interdependence but by the discrepancies and disputes experiences between and within several different states as well. Integrating diverse states into participating into environmental treaty regimes is one of the fundamental challenges today. As such, we see that three decades of environmental dialogue has successfully resulted in how the community of sovereign states has come up with a conceptual legal framework that enables burden-sharing arrangements. Also, various techniques are being adopted by industrial and developing countries in implementing international regimes. This paper asserts how differential treatment proves to be one of the most effective measures in imposing such environmental regimes as such would not undermine the capabilities of developing countries to contribute to such environmental efforts. This paper takes stock of the main findings and provides recommendations for the future enforcement of EC environmental law. Topics discussed include private enforcement against national authorities and private parties, private enforcement against Community institutions and bodies, and the Aarhus Convention.

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